

Audiovisual Sources in Space and Time

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Abstract—In article are analyzed value of audiovisual sources which possesses high integrative potential and allows studying movement of information in the history - information movement from generation to the generation, in essence providing continuity of historical development and inheritance of traditions. Information thus fixed in them is considered as a source not only about last condition of society, but also significant for programming of its subsequent activity.

Keywords—Historical source, audiovisual documents, audiovisual source, film documents, photo documents, phonodocuments, cultural heritage, National Archives, material culture, spiritual culture.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE historical experience shows, that for knowledge of the environmental world and transfer of daily experience to the subsequent generations, the mankind has learned to code the information in various material carriers. These fixed sources of the information have been intended for its transfer in space and in time, as a way of getting of the information about human community, as facilities of the social communications. To synthesize and to order the information about a reality in time and in space, to show them to us in their connecting and sequence, the mankind invented for this purpose various means. They are pictures, writing, typing of book, photo, cinema, sound recording. Abundantly clearly, that without the manipulation with these sources the knowledge of a reality is impossible.

II. THE MAIN PART

A. The Information Society and Audiovisual Documents

The modern life is accompanied by expansion of volumes of the information and channels of its distribution in a society. Thus there are qualitative changes in ways of storage of the information, changes in its transfer and distribution, which, first of all, are connected with technical discoveries. This law

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is found out in complication of structure, increase of quantity and kinds of sources in process of development of a society. Discovery of a photo, cinema, telegraph etc. might be considered as occurrence of new channels of transfer of the information and new ways of its fixing. So, the occurrence of a photo has caused to life such new kind of historical sources, as the photo documents, and then – documentary films and etc. Thus, due to technical discoveries made on a boundary XIX-XX cc., channels of transfer of the information considerably have extended, that was accompanied by increasing of volumes of the transmitted information and occurrence of new ways of its fixing. So each new channel of transfer of the information causes new ways of its fixing and storage [4]. The distribution of new kinds of historical sources - photo, audio-, video documents is connected with the ways of fixing of information. The information fixed in them, acts as a historical source of cultural development of society at the certain stage and basic channel of this development. The social cultural development of society is submitted as representational (photographic) and sound (on the phonograph) and representational sound (cinema) information and it is inherited in the form of social experience and promotes occurrence of social memory. These sources have a large integrative potential and allow studying diachronic movement of information in the history – the movement of the information from generation to generation ensuring continuity of historical development and inheritance of traditions. Thus the information, fixed in them, is considered as a source not only about the previous condition of society, but also as significant for programming its subsequent ability to live. Nowadays in historical experience the basic object of study by restoring the picture of the past are remained the traditional kinds of historical sources carrying on this or that information (direct or indirect) about left event. Actually all that volume of knowledge, which the historian gets on the basis of study of these sources about the last life, represents isolated and scattered fragments. The further development of technical means of compilation and preservation of the information, the means of the communications render influence on safety of social memory, filling of source of base of historical researches. Here before it there is in complete growth of its most important task. All usual complex of problems connected to study of time as a category of historical discourse, today can't be investigated rather deeply and comprehensively without the reference to the diversified historical sources both documentary, and art - aesthetic character (audiovisual documents), irrespective of their origin and carrier of the information [5].

B. Audiovisual Documents in the Structure of Historical Knowledge

The place and role of the audiovisual documents in structure of historical knowledge, analysis of realities of cultural and social development of society are not rethought; it is determined by traditional representations about the historical document. The value of the audiovisual documents from the historical point of view in many respects is determined in breadth and variety of the submitted information about political and cultural life of the country. The originality of technogenic documents (cinema, - photo, - etc. documents), determined by their technical, technological and other features, ability of the audiovisual documents to inform the information the phenomena of a social history and history of spiritual culture have put forward problems of organization of their state storage. By the main storehouse of these documents having the special historical, art, cultural importance is the Central State Archive of film documentary photographs and sound recordings of Republic of Kazakhstan (CGA KFDZ RK), organized in 1943 [1].

Chronologically they cover the end XIX of century (photo documents) till 90th years of XX of century. Into the structure of archive the film documentary photographs are included, formed during the activity of establishments and private persons having special value for society and uniqueness of the contents. And substantial (information) value of the document, its historical, art and culturological importance were a determining attribute allowing referring it to the category of archival sources, providing thus their safe and long storage. The National Fund of the audiovisual documents today makes a base of spiritual and material assets of our society and provides safety and availability of sources to the various purposes.

According to the Law of Republic of Kazakhstan "About National archival fund and archives" from December 22, 1998 the film documentary photographs enter and they are the integral part of information system of the state [2]. Information potential of stored sources is invaluable and concerns all aspects of ability to live of society. Unfortunately, nowadays in native historiography there are no scientific works, where the audiovisual documents would be used as high-grade historical sources alongside with the traditional written certificates. The historians with reference to a subject of the researches also pass by attention of an informative opportunity of representational sources. The expansion of sphere of use of audiovisual sources as equal in rights elements of actual base of historical researches is still in the long term.

The value of the audiovisual documents from the historical point of view in many respects is determined in breadth and variety of the submitted information about political and cultural life of the country. Acting as a uniform complex of historical sources, they have high enough informative properties, transferring their specific methods [3]. The problems of the deep and all-round analysis both estimations of information opportunities and prospects of use of audiovisual sources are represented urgent on the modern

moment. The audiovisual fund of our country contains valuable, sometimes unique information on all parties of socio economic, political, cultural life occurring in the Kazakhstan society. The central place in study of the audiovisual documents of National archival fund of the country as a historical base of historical researches occupies a question of its structure and contents. This question is one of poorly developed in Kazakhstan historical and source study literature. Despite of the recognition of the audiovisual documents as powerful information means and information product, the substantial value of these sources remains unattractive for historical community.

From all versions of audiovisual sources the film-magazines concerning the majority of the parties of activity of a community have the variety of document information. As a rule, the film-magazines represent periodic film-release, that content usually the operative film-information on various events occurring in the country. The similar information was issued regularly in the form of a film-magazine "Soviet Kazakhstan" which is stored in funds of archive since 1936. It is not only significant file in a quantitative sense in national archive, but also the source of extraordinary completeness showing the large internal and international events, separate facts from life of the ordinaries of the people. Historic information potential of these sources constantly attracts attention of the users.

Having properties to fix visible, dynamical and aural image of real life, the film photo documents was embodied by the time of a history, invaluable annals of life of a community. Today it is impossible to overestimate the events of a history, shape of the historical persons, figures of culture and science, people of different nations and trades, reliability of environment, of conditions, of costumes kept by a film. Historical importance of documentary shootings grows in due course: the film stores in itself movement of previous times, image of the people in their originality. The past thanking authenticity of film photo documents becomes the spiritual property of present, is perceived visible and quite often art accustoms by new generations [6].

The created audiovisual documentation is not deprived influences of prevailing ideology, and more often is a product of ideological propagation, but, despite of it, it remains by the important document of epoch. In connection with the huge importance of the audiovisual documents as sources of knowledge there is a urgent and perspective problem not only organizations of their storage, but also subsequent source of study [7]. This problem is multidimensional enough and it also includes set of independent themes. Among them the special importance are getting the questions of source study of an estimation of the audiovisual documents, on which sanction the creation of high-grade base of documentary sources and development of theoretical and applied researches in this area are depend.

III. CONCLUSION

Despite of the certain achievement in study of the audiovisual documents, nevertheless, in historical experience

till nowadays by basic object of study at attempt to restore a picture of the past the traditional sources are used. Our reference to source study of potential of the audiovisual documents is dictated by aspiration to pay attention the historians - researchers to their source study of the information and expansion of documentary base of researches. The misestimating of information potential of audiovisual sources on the modern moment is obvious, though the roughly developing phenomena of a civilization force to join new documentary resources (in particular in connection with introduction and distribution of technetronic and electronic documents) and puts source study problems.

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